

A Titrimetric Method for the Determination of Oxalic and Malonic Acids in a Mixture

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Oxalic and malonic acids can be oxidised quantitatively to carbon dioxide and water when refluxed for 120 min in $>1.5 M$ sulphuric acid medium in the presence of four times the thallium(III) required for the quantitative oxidation. In the photochemical oxidation of the mixture only oxalic acid is oxidised while malonic acid remains unaffected when a chloride concentration, three times (or above) that of thallium(III) is present. Basing on this fact a convenient titrimetric method is described for the analysis of mixtures of oxalic and malonic acids. In this method the thallium(I) formed is determined bromatometrically using methyl orange or brilliant ponceaux 5R as indicator. The indicator correction is negligible.

Berka *et al.*¹ analysed the mixture of oxalic and malonic acids with potassium permanganate. So far this seems to be the only titrimetric method reported for the analysis of this mixture. This method is based on the stepwise selective oxidation of the acids in alkaline and acid media and involves a laborious process.

In an earlier communication utilising the photochemical thallimetric oxidation of oxalic acid, the authors reported a method for the determination of oxalic acid². Similarly, utilising the thermal thallimetric oxidation of malonic acid a convenient titrimetric method has been described for the estimation of malonic acid³. In continuation of the investigations, the authors have studied the photochemical oxidation of malonic acid, the second member of the dicarboxylic acid series, which eventually lead to the development of a simple and accurate method for the analysis of a mixture containing oxalic and malonic acids.

Results and Discussion

The photochemical thallimetric oxidation of oxalic acid is catalysed by chloride ions when the thallium(III) to chloride molar ratio is in the range of 10 : 1 to 1 : 10. Even though the photochemical oxidation of malonic acid does not proceed to completion, the percentage of oxidation of malonic acid taking place when the reaction mixture is exposed to light for 150 min (Table 3), indicates that chloride catalysis is observed up to a thallium(III) to chloride ratio of 1 : 1. At the ratio of 1 : 2, retardation is observed and at the ratio of 1 : 3 and above, the oxidation of malonic acid is completely stopped.

Therefore, when a mixture of oxalic acid and malonic acid is exposed to the light for 10 min in the presence of excess of thallium(III), and maintaining thallium(III) to chloride molar ratio of 1 : 3 in the reaction mixture, only oxalic acid

should be oxidised leaving malonic acid unaffected. But the actual experiments have shown that instead of 10 min, a 20 min exposure time is required for the complete oxidation of oxalic acid when present along with malonic acid. So photochemically it is possible to oxidise oxalic acid selectively leaving malonic acid unaffected.

Refluxing for about 120 min in 1.5 M or more of sulphuric acid medium with four times the excess of thallium(III) required for quantitative oxidation, brings out complete oxidation of malonic acid to carbon dioxide and water along with that of oxalic acid. Therefore, known mixtures of oxalic and malonic acids are refluxed in 1.5 M sulphuric acid medium with four-times the amount of thallium(III) required for quantitative oxidation. It is observed that both oxalic acid and malonic acid are quantitatively oxidised and an equivalent amount of thallium(I) formed.

A differential titrimetric method involving photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid alone and thermal oxidation of both oxalic and malonic acids has now been described.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.25 mmol of oxalic acid and 0.0125–0.05 mmol of malonic acid, were added 1 M sulphuric acid (10 ml), chloride (3 mmol) and thallium(III) (1.0 mmol) and dilute to 75 ml. The solution was stirred and exposed to the light from mercury vapour lamp for 20 min. Hydrochloric acid (15 ml) was then added and the thallium(I) formed was titrated with potassium bromate using brilliant ponceaux 5R indicator. The titre value T_1 corresponds to the amount of oxalic acid present in the mixture.

To another aliquot of the mixture of the oxalic acid and malonic acid (the same volume of the mixture as above), were added 2.5 M sulphuric acid (45 ml) and thallium(III) (1.5 mmol) and diluted to 75 ml. The mixture was refluxed for 120

min, then cooled to 60°, concentrated HCl (15 ml) was added and titrated the thallium(I) formed with potassium bromate using brilliant ponceaux 5R indicator. The titre T_2 of potassium bromate corresponds to the total amount of malonic acid and oxalic acid. Amount of oxalic acid (mmol) = $3 \times$ molarity of potassium bromate \times volume of potassium bromate (T_1). Amount of malonic acid (mmol) = $0.75 \times$ molarity of potassium bromate \times difference in volumes of potassium bromate ($T_2 - T_1$).

Following this procedure the results of analysis of eight synthetic mixtures of the two acids of varying mole ratios (ox : mol = 1 : 1 to 1 : 20) randomly composed of different concentrations of each (e.g. oxalic : 0.05–0.25, and malonic : 0.0125–0.0499 mmol) suggest that in the mixtures each of these acids can be estimated within $\pm 0.5\%$ error.

Experimental

Thallium(III) hydroxide was prepared as reported earlier and dissolved in suitable amount of perchloric or sulphuric acid and the thallium(III) content was estimated⁴.

An aqueous solution of malonic acid was prepared and standardised*. Aqueous solutions of brilliant ponceaux 5R indicator (0.1%) and methyl orange (0.1%) were used. All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Though the photochemical reactions take place much faster under direct sunlight, in view of its variable intensity, the present investigation was done using a Phillips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (200/250V–125W) as the light source. The photochemical reactions were carried out by exposing the solutions in colourless glass containers kept at a constant distance (6'') from the light source.

Photochemical oxidation of malonic acid: The photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid has already been utilised for its determination. Under similar conditions the photochemical thallimetric oxidation of oxalic acid was tried. The photochemical oxidation of malonic acid by thallium(III) was carried out in perchloric acid medium. The effect of thallium(III) concentration on the oxidation of malonic acid was studied and the results are given in Table 1. Malonic acid did not interfere in the bromatometric titration of thallium(I)³. The progress of the reaction was monitored by titrating thallium(I) formed with potassium bromate using methyl orange as indicator.

The results (Table 1) show that the photochemical oxidation of malonic acid with thallium(III) in 1.0 M perchloric acid is not complete even after exposing the mixture to the light for 540 min. There is not enough change in the percentage of oxidation even when the amount of thallium(III) is 4-times or more than that theoretically required

for complete oxidation. Further investigations on the effect of concentration of other reagents were

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF THALLIUM(III) CONCENTRATION ON PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF MALONIC ACID BY THALLIUM(III) IN DIFFERENT EXPOSURE TIME

Total vol. of reaction mixture = 100 ml, amount of malonic acid = 0.05 mmol, conc. of perchloric acid = 1.0 M

Amount of T(III) mmol	% Oxidation*	
	150 min	540 min
0.2	15	20
0.4	15	25
0.6	17	28
0.8	17	31
1.0	17	32
1.2	18	33

*Percentage of malonic acid oxidised is calculated by comparing the amount of thallium(I) formed with the theoretical value (i.e., 4 mol of thallium(III)/mol of the acid).

carried out by keeping the concentration of thallium(III) 4-times to that theoretically required for complete oxidation of malonic acid. Under these conditions, the effects of perchloric acid concentration and relative amounts of chloride and bromide were investigated. The results are recorded in Tables 2 and 3.

The results (Tables 2 and 3) indicate that the oxidation of malonic acid by thallium(III) does not take place quantitatively to carbon dioxide and water. Even the presence of chloride or bromide that turned out to be effective catalysts in the photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid could not

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PERCHLORIC ACID CONCENTRATION ON PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF MALONIC ACID BY THALLIUM(III) IN DIFFERENT EXPOSURE TIME

Total vol. of reaction mixture = 100 ml, amount of malonic acid = 0.05 mmol, amount of thallium(III) = 0.8 mmol

[Perchloric acid] M	% Oxidation*	
	150 min	540 min
0.5	18	33
1.0	17	31
2.0	9	25
3.0	7	13
4.0	7	10

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CHLORIDE AND BROMIDE ON PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF MALONIC ACID BY THALLIUM(III) IN DIFFERENT EXPOSURE TIME

Total vol. of the reaction mixture = 100 ml, amount of thallium(III) = 0.8 mmol, amount of malonic acid = 0.05 mmol, concn. of perchloric acid = 1.0 M

Amount of chloride/bromide* mmol	In presence of chloride		% Oxidation In presence of bromide	
	150 min	540 min	150 min	540 min
0.00	17	31	18	31
0.04 (20 : 1)	18	40	20	35
0.08 (10 : 1)	19	62	24	40
0.16 (5 : 1)	20	63	30	44
0.20 (4 : 1)	25	60	36	46
0.40 (2 : 1)	25	60	36	57
0.80 (1 : 1)	25	60	36	40
1.60 (1 : 2)	3	6	5	8
2.4 (1 : 3)	Nil	2	2	7

*Thallium(III) to chloride or bromide molar ratios are given in parenthesis.

bring out the quantitative oxidation. The photochemical reaction of thallium(III) takes place much faster under sunlight as compared to the artificial daylight source in the laboratory. But even after exposing the reaction mixtures to bright sunlight for 18 h only about 60% of the reaction is completed. Hence, it may be concluded that either photochemical oxidation of malonic acid by thallium(III) in 1.0 M perchloric acid medium is very slow or the oxidation is not leading to the ultimate oxidation products. Similar results were observed in sulphuric acid medium. So this reac-

tion can not be utilised for the estimation of malonic acid.

References

1. A. BERKA, M. KORINKOVA and J. BAREK, *Microchem. J.*, 1975, 421.
2. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, 61, 2795.
3. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Talanta*, 1984, 31, 209.
4. S. R. SAGI and K. V. RAMANA, *Talanta*, 1969, 16, 1217.
5. N. N. SHARMA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 11, 417.